

DIGITAL LITERACY BASED ENVIRONMENTAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES: OPTIMIZING DIGITAL MEDIA TO MAINSTREAM GREEN POLICIES THROUGH TIKTOK

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ABSTRACT

The development of digital media has significantly transformed the landscape of environmental communication, particularly through the emergence of short-form video platforms such as TikTok. This platform has evolved beyond a space for entertainment into a strategic medium for disseminating environmental information and mainstreaming green policies. This study aims to analyze digital literacy-based environmental communication strategies, focusing on the use of TikTok as a primary channel for the circulation of environmental information. The research employs a literature review method. The findings indicate that the effectiveness of environmental communication on TikTok is strongly influenced by users' levels of digital literacy, the quality of visual strategies, and the ability of communication actors to understand and utilize platform algorithms. TikTok has proven to be a potential medium for popularizing issues such as climate change, sustainable lifestyles, and green policies. However, the risk of environmental misinformation remains high when public digital literacy is low. In conclusion, optimizing environmental communication in digital media requires synergy between creative narrative strategies, technological understanding, and the enhancement of public digital literacy.

Keywords: Digital Literacy, Digital Media, Environmental Communication, Green Policy, Tiktok.